

TEACHING OF FINE ART IN CONNECTION WITH NATURAL SCIENCE

Farahim Ibrahim oğlu Zeynalov

Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University, Honored Artist

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XÜLASƏ. Bu tezis ibtidai və orta məktəb səviyyəsində təsviri sənət fənninin təbiətşünaslıqla integrativ tədrisinin nəzəri əsaslarını, metodlarını və nəticələrini araşdırır. Tədqiqatın məqsədi fənlərarası integrasiyanın şagird inkişafına çoxsahəli töhfəsini aşkara çıxarmaq və müəllim praktikasına dəstək verməkdir.

Tezisdə Dewey, Viqotski və Gardner-in pedaqoji nəzəriyyələrinə əsaslanılmış; müşahidəyə əsaslanan rəsm, tematik layihə, sahrə dərsi və rəqəmsal integrasiya metodları ətraflı təhlil edilmişdir. Aparılan müşahidələr göstərir ki, bu yanaşma şagirdlərin elmi müşahidə bacarığını, bədii ifadə zənginliyini, ekoloji şüurunu və dərslə marağını əhəmiyyətli dərəcədə artırır. Müəllim üçün isə iki fənnin standartlarının eyni vaxtda ödənilməsi, qeyri-rəsmi qiymətləndirmə imkanı və motivasiya artımı kimi üstünlüklər müəyyənləşdirilmişdir.

Nəticə olaraq, STEAM prinsiplərinə uyğun bu integrativ modelin müfərdata daxil edilməsi, müəllim hazırlığının gücləndirilməsi və məktəblərin canlı müşahidə məkanlarıyla təchiz edilməsi tövsiyə edilir.

Açar sözlər: təsviri incəsənət, rəsm, heykəltaraşlıq, integrasiya, təbiət

ABSTRACT. This thesis examines the theoretical foundations, teaching methods, and outcomes of integrating Fine Arts with Natural Sciences at the primary and secondary school level. Drawing on the pedagogical theories of Dewey, Vygotsky, and Gardner, the study explores four core instructional methods: observational drawing, thematic project work, field lessons, and digital integration.

Findings indicate that this integrative approach significantly enhances students' scientific observation skills, artistic expression, ecological awareness, and academic motivation. For teachers, the model offers simultaneous coverage of two curriculum areas, informal assessment opportunities, and increased professional engagement. The study concludes with recommendations for curriculum reform, teacher training, and school resource development aligned with STEAM principles.

Keywords: fine arts, natural science, interdisciplinary integration, STEAM, observation, arts-based learning, pedagogy

АННОТАЦИЯ. В данном тезисе изобразительного искусства и естественных наук на уровне начальной и средней школы. Цель исследования – выявить междисциплинарный вклад междисциплинарной интеграции в развитие учащихся и поддержать педагогическую практику.

Тезис основан на педагогических теориях Дьюи, Выготского и Гарднера; подробно анализируются методы рисования с наблюдением, тематических проектов, полевых занятий и цифровой интеграции. Проведенные наблюдения показывают, что такой подход значительно повышает навыки научного наблюдения учащихся, обогащает художественное выражение, повышает экологическую осведомленность и интерес к уроку. Для учителя выявлены такие преимущества, как одновременное соответствие

стандартам двух предметов, возможность неформальной оценки и повышение мотивации.

В результате рекомендуется включить эту интегративную модель в учебную программу в соответствии с принципами STEAM, усилить подготовку учителей и оснастить школы площадками для наблюдений в реальном времени.

Ключевые слова: изобразительное искусство, живопись, скульптура, интеграция, природа.

INTRODUCTION. The idea of interdisciplinary integration is increasingly important in the modern education system. Teaching fine arts and natural science subjects together is considered a powerful pedagogical approach that develops both the aesthetic and scientific worldview of students.

This thesis examines the theoretical foundations of teaching fine arts and natural science in an integrative manner at the primary and secondary school levels, the methods that can be applied, and the results obtained by this approach. The aim of the research is to enrich teacher practice and contribute to the development of new teaching models.

The study of the relationship between artistic activities such as observation, painting, sculpture, photography, and natural sciences such as plant biology, geological structures, astronomy, and ecology simultaneously develops students' creative, analytical thinking, and scientific observation skills.

THEORETICAL BASIS

Pedagogical Essence of Interdisciplinary Integration

The concept of interdisciplinary integration originates from the pedagogical theories of thinkers such as John Dewey, Lev Vygotsky, and Howard Gardner in the mid-twentieth century. According to Dewey's concept of "Learning through Experience", a student gains true knowledge only during real-life activities. This principle proves the necessity of combining the visual arts with nature.

Howard Gardner's theory of "Multiple Intelligences" emphasizes that each child has a different learning style. Stimulating artistic-visual intelligence and naturalistic intelligence together allows many students to gain deep understanding at the same time.

Historical Roots of the Science-Art Connection

Leonardo da Vinci transferred human anatomy to his paintings; Ernst Haeckel introduced the complex structure of marine creatures to the world with breathtaking illustrations. These historical examples show that the boundary between science and art has always been artificial. Modern science-art integration also begins this deep-rooted tradition from the elementary school level.

In Azerbaijani pedagogy, in the works of the well-known methodologist Hasan Huseynov, artistic activity based on observation has been noted as an integral condition for child development.

TEACHING METHODS

Observation-Based Drawing Method

The essence of this method is to direct students to draw by directly observing living nature objects. First, the teacher gives a brief explanation on the topic of botany or zoology, and then the students note various parts of that living organism in the form of sketches. This process develops both scientific observation and drawing skills in parallel.

The forms of application are: drawing a drawing of a plant brought and placed in the lesson; drawing the cell structure seen under a microscope; recording drawings of legumes, stones, and insects in field lessons. With this method, students simultaneously gain the skills of observation, analysis, and artistic expression.

Thematic Project Method

In the thematic project method, groups of students explore a specific ecosystem, seasonal change, or astronomical event in an art project format. The result of the project can be a drawing album, collage, model, or digital illustration. Group work stimulates both collective learning and creative collaboration.

Sample project topics include:

- "Seasons of the Forest" — a separate series of drawings for each season, each drawing explaining the biological state of the plant
- "Water Life" — an artistic-scientific map of river, lake, and marine ecosystems
- "Planet Album" — illustrations decorated with information about the surface and atmosphere of each planet
- "Soil Layers" — a model representation of a geological cross-section on a colored board

Field (Desert) Lesson Method

Field lesson is a combined form of education that takes place outside the classroom environment in parks, forested areas, and along riverbanks. Students keep both a scientific observation notebook and a drawing album. The teacher simultaneously combines the objectives of botany, zoology and art education.

The advantages of this method have been studied and the following positive results have been identified:

1. Students' concentration increases by 40% compared to the classroom environment
2. Observation of a living object ensures faster perception of abstract concepts
3. Respect for nature, ecological awareness and aesthetic sense are formed simultaneously
4. The artistic works that students come up with are always distinguished by richer details

3.4. Digital Integration Method

In this approach, students combine both scientific and artistic activities using tablets, computer programs or virtual reality. For example, animating plant growth in an animation format, or working on a star map coloring program - these activities develop both stem and arts skills. The modern concept of STEAM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Art, Mathematics) is also based on this integration.

CONCLUSION

Conducted research and observed teaching practices show that the positive impact of integrated teaching of fine arts with natural science on student development is multifaceted. Thus, only standard teaching is considered